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Second generation room-temperature dual-mode photodiodes with record-low uncertainties

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Abstract

The dual-mode method enables self-calibration of photodiodes by combining a photocurrent measurement with an electrical-substitution measurement of the absorbed optical power. Recent developments have focused on reducing thermal non-equivalence between optical and electrical heating, which limits accuracy through unwanted dependencies on beam position, power level and operating temperature. In this work, we present a new generation of dual-mode modules designed to improve thermal symmetry through a backside resistive heater, a redesigned thermal conduction path and an assembly approach optimized for manufacturability. The new design also facilitates the implementation of the dual-mode method with photodiodes based on materials other than silicon. We characterize the modules experimentally and with finite-element simulations. The measurements show a substantial reduction in position-dependent non-equivalence, from 230 ppm mm⁻¹ for the previous generation to no significant dependency for the new generation. The measurements also reveal a clearly measurable dependence on optical power and relative temperature. These two effects are quantified and used to correct the apparent internal quantum deficiency (IQD). The resulting corrected IQD when measuring at the center of the diode with 748 μW optical power is $-73 \text{ ppm} \pm 34 \text{ ppm}$ ($k = 1$), consistent with simulations and representing the lowest uncertainty achieved with room-temperature dual-mode photodiodes to date. Remaining discrepancies between simulations and measurements highlight the need for improved thermal modeling, particularly regarding radiative coupling. The results demonstrate that the revised module design provides a robust pathway toward compact self-calibrating photodiodes with uncertainties equivalent to those of cryogenic radiometers.

1. Introduction

In 2014, the dual-mode method was introduced as a technique for calibrating photodiodes, specifically to determine their spectral responsivity [1]. Spectral responsivity quantifies the electrical current (in amperes) generated by a photodiode per watt of incident optical power. The method is named for its two modes of operation: a photocurrent measurement (to determine the generated current) and an electrical substitution measurement (to determine the incident optical power). Electrical substitution, a technique known primarily from cryogenic radiometry, compares the absorbed optical power to

an equivalent electrical power using a thermistor to monitor the temperature of an absorbing element.

By combining these two approaches with the same photodiode for the same incident optical power, the dual-mode method is an experimental technique which we have shown can be realized at room temperature for calibrating photodiodes, enabling their use in precise optical power measurements. Furthermore, this technique offers significant advantages over the state-of-the-art primary standard for optical power measurements using cryogenic electrical substitution radiometers. Not only does it eliminate the need for cryogenic operation, it also facilitates integration into compact instruments and allows for deployment in

remote or field-based environments. The dual-mode method provides an experimental means to measure the internal quantum deficiency (IQD), which is a key parameter of a real photodiode in comparison to an ideal photodiode. Precise IQD measurements requires that the dual-mode setup is carefully optimized to minimize differences between optical and electrical heating, i.e. the non-equivalence.

The method has been under continuous development since it was first proposed by White *et al* in 2014. In our previous work [2], we demonstrated uncertainties as low as 300 ppm ($k = 2$) at room temperature, which is comparable to those achieved with state-of-the-art cryogenic radiometers [3]. In that study, we also introduced an algorithm for correcting temperature fluctuations at the photodiode, caused by changes in ambient temperature, using a monitor thermistor. Further, we highlighted the importance of propagating absolute rather than relative uncertainties. Despite these improvements, the results remain limited by systematic effects, particularly thermal non-equivalence between optical and electrical heating and a power-dependent apparent IQD. Thermal non-equivalence causes the measured IQD to vary with the beam position on the photodiode. In dual-mode modules developed in the chipS-CALe project [4], electrical heating was achieved by forward-biasing the diode, causing heat dissipation primarily at the diode edges. In contrast, optical heating occurs at the beam spot. Accurate determination of IQD requires the thermistor to read the same temperature regardless of heating mode. Differences in thermal profiles, and therefore radiation losses, thus introduce an apparent IQD that depends on beam position.

The thermal non-equivalence challenge has been addressed in the S-CALe Up project [5], which has led to an improved module design offering better equivalence between electrical and optical heating. These new modules are presented in the paper at hand, and demonstrate a substantial reduction in thermal non-equivalence leading to record-low uncertainties of 34 ppm of the measured IQD. An important design improvement is the integration of a resistive heater on the backside of the diode, which serves as the heat source during electrical substitution. The new design also facilitates the implementation of the dual-mode method with photodiodes based on materials other than silicon. The low uncertainties we present demonstrate the potential of improving uncertainties in spectral regions outside the visible. In the design process, particular emphasis was placed on packaging strategies that support manufacturability and efficient upscaling.

We also revisit the previously observed power dependence of the apparent IQD, which has not been fully understood until now. The previous results are

now interpreted in the context of radiative heat losses, which scale non-linearly with temperature. The paper further proposes improvements to the experimental setup to mitigate this effect.

2. Theory

A brief overview of the dual-mode calibration technique is given below; for further details, the reader is referred to [2].

In photodiode calibration, the key parameter of interest is the *spectral responsivity* $R(\lambda)$, defined as the ratio of photocurrent I_{photo} to incident optical power Φ . It is expressed as

$$R(\lambda) = \frac{I_{\text{photo}}}{\Phi} = \frac{e\lambda}{hc} (1 - \delta(\lambda)) (1 - \rho(\lambda)) \gamma(\lambda), \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength, e is the elementary charge, h is Planck's constant, and c is the speed of light in vacuum. The terms $\delta(\lambda)$, $\rho(\lambda)$, and $\gamma(\lambda)$ represent the internal losses, reflectance, and quantum yield of the detector, respectively.

Because the photodiode in this study is silicon-based and operated in the spectral range above 480 nm, a single photon cannot generate more than one electron-hole pair [6]. The quantum yield $\gamma(\lambda)$ is thus effectively one and does not need to be included in the subsequent analysis.

During self-calibration, we are only concerned with the *absorbed* optical power, which is identical in both modes of dual-mode operation. Thus, reflectance $\rho(\lambda)$ can be disregarded for this purpose. However, if the calibrated photodiode is later used for absolute optical power measurements, reflectance must be taken into account. There are well-established methods to both reduce and model reflectance [7–9].

Our primary goal in determining the spectral responsivity is therefore to evaluate the internal losses, referred to as the IQD, $\delta(\lambda)$. Rearranging equation (1) yields

$$\delta(\lambda) = 1 - \frac{I_{\text{photo}}}{\Phi} \cdot \frac{hc}{e\lambda}, \quad (2)$$

which shows that the internal losses can be determined by measuring the photocurrent and the absorbed optical power. The dual-mode method achieves this by combining two independent measurements: one of the photocurrent and one of the optical power, in order to determine the IQD.

However, the true IQD of the photodiode, δ , is superimposed with additional non-equivalences arising from unwanted differences between optical and electrical heating in the dual-mode module. The apparent IQD measured and presented in

this paper, δ_a , therefore represents the sum of the intrinsic photodiode IQD, δ and these additional non-equivalences (here represented by γ),

$$\delta_a = \delta + \gamma. \quad (3)$$

Hence, an important goal is to understand, reduce and correct for these unwanted, additional non-equivalences γ .

The photocurrent measurement is relatively straightforward and is performed conventionally, applying a reverse bias to the diode and with the dark current subtracted. The main challenge lies in determining the absorbed optical power Φ . To do this, we employ the concept of *electrical substitution*.

During electrical substitution, the photodiode is heated either optically (via irradiation) or electrically (via a resistive heater on its backside). In previous experiments, electrical heating was achieved by operating the diode under forward bias. In the new design, an external resistive heater is used instead, and the photodiode remains a passive element (open circuit) throughout the electrical substitution measurement.

Electrical substitution can be implemented in either *closed-loop* or *open-loop* configurations. Closed-loop operation involves maintaining a constant temperature during the switch from optical to electrical heating, using a feedback control system. In this study, however, we employ an open-loop approach. Here, the electrical heating is applied at two levels: one above and one below the optical heating level. This results in three distinct temperature states. The known electrical power levels and thermistor resistances are then used in combination with a linear interpolation to derive the unknown optical power Φ :

$$\Phi = \frac{R_{\text{opt}} - R_1}{R_2 - R_1} (U_2 I_2 - U_1 I_1) + U_1 I_1, \quad (4)$$

where R_x denotes the thermistor resistance at each condition: $x = 1$ and $x = 2$ for electrical heating levels below and above the optical heating level, and $x = \text{opt}$ for optical heating. U and I are the voltage across and current through the resistive heater, respectively.

Further information on the dual-mode method and electrical substitution using photodiodes can be found in [1, 2, 10].

3. Methods

3.1. New dual-mode modules

The photodiodes used to manufacture the dual-mode modules were designed and manufactured in the chipS-CALe project [4]. These diodes have an

active area of $14 \times 11 \text{ mm}^2$, and well characterized internal losses in the order of 10 ppm. The known low IQD makes these photodiodes well-suited as a reference when developing this method. The dual-mode modules were designed based on the following requirements: (1) non-equivalence lower than 300 ppm and sensitivity to beam alignment lower than 100 ppm mm^{-1} , (2) structure consisting of commercially available components, and (3) possibility of using an assembly procedure consisting of few steps, while allowing devices with low sensitivity to variation in fabrication.

As shown previously [2], the use of forward bias heating and an asymmetric device structure led to a relatively high non-equivalence and beam position dependence (230 ppm mm^{-1}), primarily caused by the difference in thermal emission between the optical and electrical heating modes.

Therefore, a new design was developed based on two principles: (1) a resistive heater on the backside of the photodiode is used to obtain a heating profile similar to that in the optical mode, and (2) the thermally conductive link to the photodiode has several attachment points symmetrically placed a distance away from the photodiode center in order to reduce the sensitivity to beam alignment and heating mode.

Thermal and thermo-electrical simulations in COMSOL Multiphysics were used to design the dual-mode detector (DMD) structure consisting of a PCB which serves as the thermally conducting link between the photodiode and heat sink in addition to assessing the sensitivity to other design parameters such as bonding materials and layer thicknesses. The resulting PCB design is thermally (conductively) coupled to the photodiode in four corners as indicated in figure 1. Otherwise the PCB is separated by a thin gap ($< 100 \mu\text{m}$) except for 5 wire bonds; two connecting the PCB to the backside heater and three connecting the front photodiode connections to the PCB. A narrow section of the PCB forms the weak link to the heat sink and includes the copper traces for the heater and thermistor. An off-the-shelf wire-bondable 1000Ω (Vishay Electro-films PWA10000FKANHT5) resistive heater was chosen. Although a higher resistance would be desirable to limit parasitic heating from the input current, the resulting non-equivalence due to this effect was determined to be on an acceptable level in the order of 10 ppm.

A $10 \text{ k}\Omega$ surface mount device thermistor serves as the temperature sensor used to measure the thermal response of the DMD. It is placed near the weak link in a position determined to have the lowest non-equivalence and sensitivity to beam alignment, as indicated in figure 5. A thermistor of the same type

Figure 1. (a) CAD model of the DMD module viewed from the back side (left) and front side (right) of the photodiode. The PCB substrate and passivating layers and copper traces are colored green and yellow respectively. The diameter of the wire bonds have been scaled by factor of 2 in the right figure for better clarity. (b) shows the vertical crosssection of the assembly along the dashed line i (a). The figure has been scaled in the vertical direction (3:1) to better visualize the relative thicknesses of layers.

is mounted on the PCB to monitor the heat-sink temperature.

A numerical study was conducted to determine the sensitivity of the design to both assembly and external variables. Assembly variables include for example bonding parameters such as number and type of wire bonds as well as adhesive layer thicknesses and non-uniformity after bonding. External variables include optical parameters such as input power, beam alignment, absorption of optical power outside the photodiode, as well as the thermal coupling to the ambient surroundings, e.g. copper trap and heat sink structure and the thermal radiation between the DMD, copper trap and optical window.

Thermal radiation was simulated using COMSOLs Surface-to-surface radiation module, which calculate the mutual thermal radiation between the surfaces inside the copper trap. View factors were computed using the ray shooting algorithm in order to include the specular reflection effects. The optical window, which couples the

interior of the trap to the ambient temperature was modelled as a surface with constant isothermal temperature T_{amb} . Most results were found using the stationary solver, meaning time-dependent effects caused by the thermal inertia of the system were disregarded. Time-dependent simulations were conducted with a simplified radiation model, which was necessary in order to obtain a stable solver, where mutual interactions were excluded, giving a net emitted power for all radiating surfaces of:

$$J = \sigma \epsilon (T^4 - T_0^4) \quad (5)$$

where σ , ϵ , T and T_0 is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant, emissivity of the material, temperature of the surface element and (constant) ambient temperature respectively. The non-equivalence for a given set of parameters was found in a way equivalent to the experimental procedure: the simulated temperature difference $\Delta T_{el} = T_2 - T_1$ in the thermistor divided by the difference between the two electrical

power levels $\Delta P_{\text{el}} = P_2 - P_1$ defines the thermal responsivity:

$$\Gamma_{\text{el}} = \Delta T_{\text{el}} / \Delta P_{\text{el}}. \quad (6)$$

The thermistor temperature (T_{opt}) in optical mode for an optical input power (Φ), where ($P_{\text{L}} < \Phi < P_{\text{H}}$) is used to calculate the power level $\hat{\Phi}_{\text{opt}}$ corresponding to the experimental procedure:

$$\hat{\Phi}_{\text{opt}} = P_{\text{L}} + 1/\Gamma_{\text{el}} \cdot (T_{\text{opt}} - T_1). \quad (7)$$

Non-equivalence is defined as the relative difference between the calculated and true optical power level Φ :

$$\gamma = (\hat{\Phi}_{\text{opt}} - \Phi) / \Phi. \quad (8)$$

3.2. Experimental setup

The dual-mode module is mounted on a copper carrier (see figure 4(c)), which is positioned at a 45° angle on a copper trap (upper part of assembly in figure 5(b); further details in [10]). The photodiode is irradiated with a power controlled HeNe laser (Melles Griot 05-LHP-991, wavelength 632.99 nm), with the beam path shown in figure 2. At the detector, the 1/e² beam diameter is measured to 2.48 mm, corresponding to a projected diameter of 3.51 mm on the detector surface in the vertical direction. A mirror inside the trap redirects the reflected beam from the module back onto the photodiode. Beneath the trap, a Peltier element and a Pt1000 sensor used for temperature control are installed. The Peltier element, controlled by a Thorlabs TED 350, regulates the temperature of the trap and the dual-mode module relative to the ambient temperature. The trap assembly is housed inside a vacuum cube (ideal vacuum products), with optical access provided through an antireflection-coated window to minimize reflection losses at the input. The vacuum chamber is evacuated to the 1×10^{-6} mbar range using an Agilent TPS-mini KF40. The vacuum cube is placed on top of a lab jack, allowing one to vary the beam position on the diode. The vertical beam position is controlled using a dial indicator with 10 μm resolution. Using edge detection to align the beam to the center of the diode has proven excellent reproducibility. The beam position y is referenced to the center of the diode ($y = 0$ mm) and the positive direction as shown in figure 1.

The electrical configuration is shown in figure 3. A Datron 4700 calibrator was used as the voltage source for the heater circuit, while a SIM928 (Stanford Research Systems) was used as a source for the photocurrent circuit. The resistance of the diode thermistor and the monitor thermistor was measured in a four-wire configuration using a SIM921 AC resistance bridge (Stanford Research Systems) and in a two-wire

configuration using a Keysight 3458A digital multimeter, respectively. The voltage across the heater was measured using a Keithley 2002 digital multimeter.

Two different configurations were used for measuring the currents. In the first configuration, the photocurrent and the heater current were measured using two separate Femto DLPCA-200 transimpedance amplifiers (TIAs) (see figure 3(a)). This approach requires both instruments to be stable and well-calibrated to avoid introducing apparent biases in the derived IQD values due to offsets or gain mismatches. During this study, a drift in the proportionality factor of −0.02% over a time period of five months was observed for one of the TIAs. Consequently, it became necessary to develop an improved approach. In the improved configuration, a single current measurement path was used: both currents were measured either by monitoring the voltage drop across a single $1000.0536 \Omega \pm 0.0004 \Omega$ standard resistor, or by use of a single TIA (see figure 3(b)). Using a standard resistor is particularly advantageous, as it completely eliminates instrument offset contributions and gain non-linearity. Any drift in resistance calibration value influences both modes similarly, and does not influence the apparent IQD values.

Using only one current measurement device for both circuits is enabled by the fact that the two sources are not operated simultaneously. When the source in the heater circuit is active, the source in the diode circuit is open source, and vice versa. With the setup depicted in figure 3(b), the resulting voltage signal (TIA output or voltage drop over standard resistor) were measured using the same digital voltmeter used for the heater voltage. The digital voltmeter was calibrated prior to the measurements, and the recorded values were corrected.

3.3. Measurement sequence

The measurement sequence follows the procedure described in [2] and is summarized here for convenience.

The measurement cycle starts with a photocurrent measurement. To obtain the photocurrent I_{photo} , the current with the laser incident on the diode is recorded, I_{light} , and the dark current I_{dark} is subtracted:

$$I_{\text{photo}} = I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}. \quad (9)$$

During each measurement run, the following steps are performed while current in the active circuit, voltage drop over the heater, diode and monitor thermistor resistances are logged:

1. **Measurement of I_{light} (1.5 min):** the shutter is open, and the current I_{light} is measured with the beam incident on the diode. The diode is reverse biased between 7 and 10 V, depending on the optical power level.

2. **Measurement of I_{dark} (1.5 min):** the shutter is closed, and the current I_{dark} is measured with the diode still reverse biased.
3. **Temperature stabilization (20 min):** the shutter is open and the diode is left in open circuit, allowing the device to reach the temperature corresponding to optical heating.
4. The following **electrical-substitution** sequence a–d is repeated five times before a new light and dark current measurement is performed:
 - a. **Low electrical heating (20 min):** the shutter is closed and the heater power is set to about $10 \mu\text{W}$ below the estimated optical heating level.
 - b. **Optical heating (20 min):** the shutter is open, the heater is in open circuit, and the diode is heated optically.
 - c. **High electrical heating (20 min):** the shutter is closed and the heater power is set to about $10 \mu\text{W}$ above the estimated optical heating level.
 - d. **Optical heating (20 min):** optical heating is repeated.

The full measurement series 1–4 is repeated multiple times (three to nine). To compute the apparent IQD, the thermistor resistances at the low electrical heating level (R_1), the high heating level (R_2)

Figure 4. (a) The copper trap is mounted on top of a Peltier element, which itself is mounted on a copper base. This assembly is placed inside the vacuum cube. (b) Copper aperture mounted on the copper trap. (c) Dual-mode module mounted on copper carrier. (d) Copper carrier with a hole drilled above the backside heater.

and the optical heating level (R_{opt}) are computed from the resistance data (details below). The corresponding heater voltages and currents at the low and high heating steps (U_1, I_1 and U_2, I_2) are obtained from the voltage and current data. Repeating the electrical-substitution sequence five times results in a total of ten apparent IQD estimates: five obtained during the step-up power transitions and five during the step-down transitions. The photocurrent assigned to each optical heating interval is obtained by linearly interpolating between the photocurrent measurements performed before and after the electrical substitution sequences.

3.4. Data analysis

After data acquisition, different approaches can be used to determine the apparent IQD. These approaches differ in how the optical power Φ is inferred from the thermistor resistance. Two methods have been proposed: the *average method* and

the *exponential-fit method*. The average method uses the mean resistance after the thermistor has reached steady state (typically the final two minutes of each step). The exponential-fit method instead fits the temperature transient between heating levels to an exponential response, from which the asymptotic resistance is extracted. The exponential-fit method thus utilizes a larger fraction of the available data compared with the average method. We observe that the apparent IQD estimate depends on the chosen evaluation method. For consistency with previous work, we use the exponential-fit method throughout this paper. A dedicated study of the signal-processing choices is left for future work.

A further important aspect of the analysis is the correction for temperature fluctuations. Due to variations in ambient temperature, the diode temperature typically changes by 30–40 mK over a measurement series. Earlier work attempted to stabilize the

temperature using the Peltier element beneath the copper trap. However, as will be shown in the next section, changing the operating temperature of the device affects the result. In addition, active regulation introduced additional fluctuations that were difficult to correct for and therefore increased the uncertainty of the estimated IQD. For most measurements, the module was therefore left near room temperature, and temperature variations were monitored using the dedicated thermistor on the module PCB.

For measurements intentionally performed at temperatures different from room temperature, the temperature controller was operated in an overdamped mode, such that the device temperature approached but never reached the setpoint. This approach avoided the regulation-induced oscillations that were difficult to correct for.

As the temperature signal propagates thermally from the monitor location to the diode thermistor, it becomes delayed and increasingly smoothed due to thermal diffusion, with higher-frequency components more strongly attenuated. To reproduce this behavior, a running-mean filter is applied to the monitor thermistor signal, followed by a temporal shift. A window of 671 s and a delay of 93 s yielded the lowest uncertainties in the analysis. After smoothing and time-shifting, the processed monitor signal is subtracted from the diode thermistor signal. An optional scaling factor can be applied if the response of the monitor thermistor and the diode thermistor differ. Further details on the temperature-correction procedure are given in [2].

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Simulations

Figure 5 shows an example of simulated non-equivalence and thermal responsivity ($\Gamma = \Delta T/P$) viewed from the backside of the module. The thermal resistance caused by the thin adhesive layer and the effect of the bonding wires lead to high (> 1000 ppm) non-equivalence in parts of the PCB. However, due to the narrow width ($\approx 76 \mu\text{m}$) of the copper lines compared to the wide lines connecting the thermistor, this is only a local effect which is reduced significantly closer to the thermistor. Additionally, the relatively higher non-equivalence seen on the photodiode itself is also caused by the Joule heating outside the resistive heater in the electrical mode. However, since this power is also accounted for when calculating the thermal response, the effect on non-equivalence is reduced. The remaining plots in figure 5 indicate the general conductive heat flow and thermal resistance through the PCB substrate and adhesive bonds, showing that the simulated heat flow is similar in both modes. The lower thermal resistance of the copper layers leads to a concentration of conductive heat flux. The noticeable

temperature drop from the photodiode to the PCB, caused by the lower thermal conductivity of the adhesive bonds and PCB substrate reduce the sensitivity to beam alignment since the relative difference in thermal resistance from any point in the photodiode to each of the four connection points is small. From the simulation results, the dependence of the calculated non-equivalence to several variables were found using a linear regression model. The parameters and variables were selected based on relevance to experiments and significance for the predicted non-equivalence:

$$\gamma = a_0 + a_1 \cdot x_1 + a_2 \cdot x_2 \dots \quad (10)$$

The results for the fit, along variable descriptions, is given in table 1 and figure 6. Of the variables related to the experimental conditions (x_1 to x_5) beam misalignment in the y -direction has by far the largest effect on non-equivalence with a simulated dependence of 66 ppm mm^{-1} , while other variables, such as power dependence and ambient temperature are smaller in comparison within the assumed variable ranges. The conductive thermal resistances to the heater (defined as $\rho = L/(kA)$ in a lumped element model) has a large effect on γ . Specifically, the ratio between the thermal resistance of the wire bonds and adhesive bond:

$$\nu = \frac{\rho_{\text{adhesive}}}{\rho_{\text{wires}}} \quad (11)$$

has a large negative effect on the simulated non-equivalence as seen in figure 6. This is caused by an increase in heat conducted through the wire bonds for increasing ν , e.g. for thicker adhesive layers or higher diameter bond wires. With the assumed thickness of the adhesive bond (around $1 \mu\text{m}$) and wire bonds parameter ($\text{Ø}30 \mu\text{m}$ Al wire bonds), the approximate value $\nu = 0.11\%$ causes an offset term in γ of -72 ppm. In future work, effort will be made to reduce and validate the value ν , for example by using thinner bond wires and ensuring a minimal bond layer thickness and/or alternative bonding materials such as metallic bonds.

The time-dependent simulations were performed for a full cycle consisting of the two electrical (high, low) and two optical levels (step down, step up). The time constant of the DMD thermistor for each step was found to be around 99 s by fitting to an exponential function, while the thermal responsivity Γ_{el} (given by equation (6)) was 408 K W^{-1} . As the corresponding responsivity in stationary results, as shown in figure 5 is higher (around 482 K W^{-1}), the simplified model therefore overestimates the radiative losses. As the time constant is roughly proportional to the thermal responsivity and the heat capacity C in a lumped model ($\tau \propto \Gamma_{\text{el}} \cdot C$), the corresponding time constant with the full radiation model would be around 117 s. As C is dominated

Figure 5. (a) Simulation result showing the calculated non-equivalence (color bar has a logarithmic scale and capped is between 10 ppm and 1000 ppm) in the DMD assembly and (b) the thermal responsivity (color bar capped at 100 K W^{-1}) for a solution with perfectly aligned optical beam. (c) Corresponding streamline plots indicating the general heat flux conduction in the DMD assembly viewed from above and from the side. Split figure with red lines showing the result for the optical mode on one half ($x < 0$) and blue lines showing the result for the electrical mode on the other half of the assembly ($x > 0$). The z axis has been scaled by 3:1 relative to the horizontal axes to improve readability.

Table 1. Simulated variable sensitivity.

Variable (unit)	Variable range	Fit constant (a_i)	Variable description
-		$a_0 = 24 \pm 32 \text{ (ppm)}$	Zero-offset
$x_1 \text{ (mW)}$	[0.5,1]	$a_1 = -11 \pm 16 \text{ (ppm mW}^{-1}\text{)}$	Optical input power (Φ)
$x_2 \text{ (mm)}$	[-1, 1]	$a_2 = 66 \pm 5 \text{ (ppm mm}^{-1}\text{)}$	Beam y -misalignment (y)
$x_3 \text{ (mm)}$	[0 1]	$a_3 = -1 \pm 12 \text{ (ppm mm}^{-1}\text{)}$	Beam x -misalignment (x)
$x_4 \text{ (K)}$	[-2 2]	$a_4 = 0.4 \pm 3.2 \text{ (K mm}^{-1}\text{)}$	Ambient temperature offset (ΔT)
$x_5 \text{ (%)}$	[1 5]	$a_5 = -4.3 \pm 2.3 \text{ (ppm/%)}$	Mirror loss (1-Reflectivity)
$x_6 \text{ (%)}$	[0.025 1.15]	$a_6 = -624 \pm 10 \text{ (ppm/%)}$	ν (equation (11))
$x_7 \text{ (}\mu\text{m)}$	[25 50]	$a_7 = -0.1 \pm 0.6 \text{ (ppm mm}^{-1}\text{)}$	thickness of PD-to-PCB adhesive layer

by the ($16.2 \text{ mm} \times 13.2 \text{ mm} \times 0.5 \text{ mm}$) silicon photodiode having a heat capacity of $C_{\text{PD}} = 0.174 \text{ J K}^{-1}$, the minimum corresponding time constant is $\tau = 482 \text{ KW}^{-1} \cdot 0.174 \text{ J K}^{-1} = 84 \text{ s}$. The higher simulated time constant is due to both the thermal resistance from the temperature sensor to the photodiode as well as the additional heat capacity of the PCB and additional components in the assembly.

4.2. Experimental results

The experimental results presented in this paper were selected from a large dataset comprising more than 100 measurement series. Several electrical configurations and experimental setups were evaluated, and the results shown here represent the cases that most clearly illustrate the trends observed.

Figure 6. (a) shows the simulated non-equivalence versus beam y -position for four values of the parameter ν according to the definition (equation 11). Markers show the data points while lines are the linear interpolation between points. (b) shows all simulation results (markers) grouped by color according to beam y -position. Dashed lines are the linear fits for each group.

Figure 7. (a) Apparent IQD δ_a from measurements at different optical power levels and at different beam positions on the diode. The uncertainty bars represent the type A standard measurement uncertainty. (b) The average apparent IQD δ_a for each optical power level is plotted against the power level and their uncertainty bars represent the standard uncertainty. The power dependence of the apparent IQD can be fitted with a linear regression as depicted.

4.2.1. Dependence of the apparent IQD on beam position and optical power levels

Measurements of the apparent IQD at different beam positions show that the new-generation dual-mode modules exhibit significantly reduced position-induced non-equivalence between electrical and optical heating compared to the previous generation. With the previous design, measurement of the apparent IQD showed a clear linear dependence on beam position of 230 ppm mm^{-1} due to unwanted position-dependent non-equivalence [2]. In contrast, the measurements in figure 7(a) with the updated module exhibit no linear trend. The average beam-position dependence is $-24.4 \pm 32.4 \text{ ppm mm}^{-1}$. Over $y = \pm 1$ mm, the average peak-to-peak spread is 113 ppm. These measurements were performed

with the aperture placed in front of the trap, with an intact copper carrier and at room temperature (no temperature regulation). A standard resistor was used to measure the current, following the configuration shown in figure 3(b). Measurements were repeated using a different module, yielding similar results (results not shown).

The results in figure 7(a) also show that the optical power level influences the apparent IQD, consistent with observations from the previous generation of dual-mode modules. By taking the weighted average of the IQD at each power level, where the weights correspond to the number of measurement points per position, and plotting the resulting values (figure 7(b)), we obtain a dependence across the measured range that can be fitted

linearly. A linear regression of these data yields a slope of $\alpha_{\Phi} = -0.334 \text{ ppm } \mu\text{W}^{-1}$ and an intercept of -88.084 ppm at $0 \text{ } \mu\text{W}$. The uncertainty of the slope is $0.026 \text{ ppm } \mu\text{W}^{-1}$.

4.2.2. Dependence of the apparent IQD on temperature

Using the Peltier element placed between the copper trap and the base, the temperature of the trap and module was regulated to three discrete points within approximately $\pm 2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ relative to the ambient temperature. As a result, the module and trap maintained a temperature offset from the surrounding vacuum cube. Measurements presented in this subsection were conducted using two TIAs to measure the current, following the configuration shown in figure 3(a).

Measurements were first conducted without an aperture mounted on the trap, as shown in figure 5(b). These measurements, plotted in blue in figure 8, revealed a pronounced dependence of the apparent IQD on the temperature of the diode relative to the surroundings. The heat dissipation from the module is combined of thermal conduction through the solid materials and radiative heat loss through the opening in the trap. To investigate the role of the radiative heat transfer, an aperture with a nominal diameter of 6.5 mm was mounted in front of the copper trap as depicted in figure 5(c), and a hole was drilled in the copper carrier (figure 4(d)).

Measurements were repeated with these modifications, resulting in the apparent IQDs shown in green in figure 8. These results clearly show that reducing radiative coupling from the DMD module to the vacuum chamber improves the temperature-sensitivity. In addition, it substantially reduces the measurement uncertainty. The reduced temperature dependence was also observed at higher optical power levels and when using an intact copper carrier (without the hole). These observations indicate that the dominant improvement comes from limiting the radiative heat transfer to the surroundings, as the front surfaces (photodiode surface and PCB front surface) have higher emissivities than the back side, which are dominated by metals having low emissivity. Although the underlying cause of the apparent IQD sensitivity to radiative transfer is not immediately evident from the measurements, based on equation (4), it must be an effect on the relative differences between the three measured temperature levels.

The simulation results presented here do not reproduce either the dependence on power level or ambient temperature. Therefore, the model currently has one or more significant discrepancies with respect to the real system which are not presently understood.

One possible cause could be the existence of slow oscillations or drifts in background temperature caused by the cycling between power level. These could be caused by the large thermal masses present in the system, e.g. the copper trap structure and walls of

the vacuum chamber, potentially leading to time constants significantly longer than that of the DMD. Such slow oscillations could affect the relative difference between the measured temperature levels, leading to the observed effect on the measured IQD. However, substantial further analysis of the measurement series would be needed in order to quantify such an effect. A more advanced simulation model could also be developed by also including modeling of the interior of the the vacuum chamber and interactions with external environment.

Another possible cause would be related to other simplifications of the model or deviance between the simulated and real material parameters. One effect could be due to the simplified modeling optical window which is modeled with a constant temperature. An improved model would include a more realistic representation of the interior of the vacuum chamber, in particular the geometry between environment between the copper trap and optical window, which affect the balance of thermal radiation.

Note that the aperture size was chosen to ensure that the incident beam reaches the active area of the diode without causing any stray light. This is also true for the investigation of beam position dependence of the apparent IQD from section 4.2.1.

4.2.3. Understanding the power level dependency of the IQD

In light of the previous section, it becomes clear why the apparent IQD depends on the power level. This effect was first reported in [2] for the previous generation of dual-mode modules, and a reprint of figure 9 from that work is shown in figure 9(a). The different electrical background powers refer to additional electrical power applied during the electrical substitution process. The optical power was maintained at $366 \text{ } \mu\text{W}$ throughout the series. Further details on the measurement procedure are provided in [2]. The origin of the power dependence is straightforward: higher power dissipation raises the diode temperature. Since radiative losses scale with the difference of the fourth power of temperature, any differences in radiative losses become increasingly pronounced as the optical power increases. A larger temperature difference between the diode and the ambient therefore increases the unwanted non-equivalence γ , particularly in measurements where the diode's field of view is unrestricted. In fact, the measurements on the previous generation were performed without an aperture in front of the diode, and figure 9(a) clearly illustrates the resulting power dependence.

When plotting the same apparent IQD as a function of the relative temperature increase at the diode compared to ambient, figure 9(b), the temperature dependence of the IQD becomes evident. Since simulations of the earlier modules predicted a thermal responsivity of 524 KW^{-1} , they underestimate both the apparent IQD offset and the stronger power

dependence observed experimentally. The experimentally observed thermal responsivity is around 1818 K W^{-1} . Because the simulations do not capture the actual temperature difference, they cannot reproduce the observed dependence.

4.2.4. Uncertainty analysis

The results presented so far reveal several effects that may influence the apparent IQD. From the experimental measurements, we observe clear dependencies on both the optical power level, Φ , and on the relative temperature difference, ΔT , between the diode and its surroundings. The simulations further predict two additional sensitivities: an offset in the IQD caused by the adhesive layer thickness between the heater and the diode (which in turn depends on the wire-bond geometry), and a dependence on beam position. The first effect does not influence the uncertainty of the measurements, but it may introduce an offset in the IQD. However, as shown below, the simulations and measurements are in good agreement, which strengthens our confidence that the estimated adhesive layer thickness is accurate. To avoid this unnecessary dependency in the future, simulations indicate that thinner bond wires are preferable. This will be taken into consideration in the design of the next-generation dual-mode modules. Further, the simulated position dependence is not supported by the measurements, which show no consistent trend (figure 7(a)). This effect is therefore also excluded from the correction.

The only two effects that are experimentally confirmed and quantifiable—the dependencies on Φ and ΔT —are thus used to correct the apparent IQD. Although both arise from variations in the thermal profile and heat transfer, it is practical to treat their contributions separately.

Taking these two effects into account, the corrected IQD δ is given by

$$\delta = \bar{\delta}_a - \alpha_\Phi \cdot \bar{\Phi} - \alpha_T \cdot \Delta T, \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\delta}_a$ is the weighted mean apparent IQD at average optical power level $\bar{\Phi}$ and temperature difference ΔT , and where α_Φ and α_T represent the sensitivities to optical power level and temperature, respectively.

To evaluate the combined uncertainty in the corrected IQD, each term in equation (12) must be considered. We begin with the average IQD from a measurement series, $\bar{\delta}_a$, and determine how the uncertainties in the quantities appearing in equation (2) propagate into the uncertainty of $\bar{\delta}_a$. To do this, we start by looking at the uncertainties in a single measurement of the apparent IQD, δ_a . For this purpose, we have selected a representative single measurement from the measurement series at $y = 0 \text{ mm}$ and optical power $750 \mu\text{W}$. The photocurrent for this single measurement is obtained as the difference between the light and dark currents (equation (9)), and the associated uncertainty budget for a single photocurrent measurement is given in table 2. For all quantities reported as average values, the uncertainty is taken to be the standard deviation of the mean.

Figure 9. (a) Reprint of figure 9 in [2]. Simulated non-equivalence γ and measured apparent IQD δ_a for different electrical background power levels and at different beam positions y . The optical power was 366 μ W. (b) The same apparent IQD δ_a as in (a), plotted against relative temperature to the ambient, ΔT , instead of beam position. Solid markers denote measurements, while hollow markers denote simulations. Reproduced from [2]. The Author(s). CC BY 4.0.

Table 2. Uncertainty budget for photocurrent I_{photo} .

X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u_i(y)$
I_{light}	3.8662178×10^{-4} A	7.5×10^{-10} A	1	7.5×10^{-10} A
I_{dark}	1.479×10^{-8} A	2.9×10^{-10} A	-1	2.9×10^{-10} A
I_{photo}	3.8660699×10^{-4} A			8.0×10^{-10} A

To determine the uncertainty in Φ , the contributions from all terms in equation (4) must be taken into account. For resistance values which are computed with the expfit-method, the uncertainty is taken to be the square root of the variance in the fitted parameter. An example uncertainty budget is shown in table 3, using values from the same measurement series as the photocurrent results shown above. As seen in the table, the uncertainty in R_{opt} is larger than that of R_1 and R_2 and has a greater sensitivity to influence the uncertainty of Φ . This is because R_{opt} includes an additional contribution arising from fluctuations in the background temperature and from variations in the laser power (see [2] for details). Note that correlations between the input quantities have not been considered. Due to the measurement setup described in section 3.2, the combined uncertainty would be reduced by correlations of the electrical quantities. Therefore, the determined uncertainty $u(\Phi)$ is a reliable, conservative estimate.

With the Type A uncertainty budgets for both I_{photo} and Φ established, the combined uncertainty can be propagated to obtain the uncertainty in δ_a .

The resulting uncertainty budget for δ_a is presented in table 4. The largest contribution arises from the uncertainty in the estimated optical power Φ , which accounts for 95% of the total.

From each measurement series, we obtain an average IQD together with its associated uncertainty of the mean (i.e. the statistical uncertainty of the average). To complete the uncertainty budget for δ , the

remaining contributions in equation (12) must also be evaluated.

Although the uncertainty of the average for each individual measurement of δ_a is low (on average 15.8 ppm), the observed spread in values over $y = \pm 1$ mm must be accounted for in the uncertainty analysis. By treating this spread as a uniform distribution with a peak-to-peak width of 113 ppm the standard uncertainty is obtained by applying a sensitivity factor of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}$ [11]. We therefore account for this effect by combining, in quadrature, the statistical measurement uncertainty with the additional uncertainty corresponding to the observed spread of 113 ppm. For the measurement series used in the uncertainty budget, the resulting uncertainty in $\bar{\delta}_a$ is 34 ppm.

The reason for the relatively large spread of IQD values observed at different beam positions, compared with the individual measurement uncertainty, is not known and is therefore treated as a square distribution based on the observed experimental results. A dedicated study to resolve this dominating uncertainty will be needed to understand the reasons for this apparently random effect. Possible causes of this spread may arise from variations in the laser power between successive photocurrent measurements, which directly influence the derived IQD. Another plausible contributor is the temperature of objects within the diode's field of view. We have previously observed that inserting an aperture in front of the trap significantly reduces the IQD's sensitivity to temperature differences between the diode

Table 3. Uncertainty budget for estimated optical power from electrical substitution, Φ , for a single IQD measurement.

X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u_i(y)$
R_1	10 398.1401 Ω	2.8×10^{-3} Ω	2.2×10^{-6} W Ω^{-1}	6.1×10^{-9} W
R_2	10 393.2365 Ω	4.8×10^{-3} Ω	1.8×10^{-6} W Ω^{-1}	8.6×10^{-9} W
R_{opt}	10 395.9535 Ω	8.7×10^{-3} Ω	-4.0×10^{-6} W Ω^{-1}	3.4×10^{-8} W
U_1	0.86 517 856 V	1.2×10^{-7} V	4.7×10^{-4} W V $^{-1}$	5.5×10^{-11} W
U_2	0.87 661 908 V	1.3×10^{-7} V	3.9×10^{-4} W V $^{-1}$	4.9×10^{-11} W
I_1	$8.6466 232 \times 10^{-4}$ A	1.0×10^{-10} A	0.48 W A $^{-1}$	4.8×10^{-11} W
I_2	$8.7609 656 \times 10^{-4}$ A	1.2×10^{-10} A	0.39 W A $^{-1}$	4.6×10^{-11} W
Φ	$7.56 968 \times 10^{-4}$ W			3.6×10^{-8} W

Table 4. Uncertainty budget for a single apparent IQD, δ_a , from a measurement series performed at $y = 0$ mm and optical power 750 μ W.

X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u_i(y)$
I_{photo}	$3.8660 699 \times 10^{-4}$ A	8.0×10^{-10} A	-2.6×10^9 ppm A $^{-1}$	2.1 ppm
Φ	$7.56 968 \times 10^{-4}$ W	3.6×10^{-8} W	1.3×10^9 ppm W $^{-1}$	48 ppm
λ	$6.329 910 \times 10^{-7}$ m	3×10^{-13} m	1.6×10^{12} ppm m $^{-1}$	0.53 ppm
δ_a	-371 ppm			48 ppm

Table 5. Uncertainty budget for the corrected IQD, δ , with a final absolute uncertainty of 34 ppm. The measurement series was conducted at 748.08 μ W without changing the temperature on the copper trap ($\Delta T = 0$ K).

X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u_i(y)$
$\bar{\delta}_a$	-323 ppm	34 ppm	1	34 ppm
α_Φ	-3.34×10^5 ppm W $^{-1}$	2.6×10^4 ppm W $^{-1}$	-1.1×10^{-6} W	2.8×10^{-2} ppm
Φ	7.481×10^{-4} W	1.1×10^{-6} W	-2.6×10^4 ppm W $^{-1}$	2.8×10^{-2} ppm
α_T	-69.0 ppm K $^{-1}$	8.8 ppm K $^{-1}$	-0.1 K	0.88 ppm
ΔT	0.0 K	0.1 K	-8.8 ppm K $^{-1}$	0.88 ppm
δ	-73 ppm			34 ppm

and the ambient environment, suggesting that objects within the diode's field of view can affect the apparent IQD through radiative effects. The iris, having a comparatively low thermal mass, may therefore introduce additional variation if its temperature fluctuates. Although monitoring the iris temperature could help confirm this hypothesis, such measurements are expected to be labor intensive and are therefore left for a future study. Since the current spread appears random, we treat it as such. This represents a conservative approach, which we consider appropriate until further data reveal any systematic components that could be corrected for.

The relative standard uncertainty $u(\Phi)$ in the optical power level is taken as the average observed standard deviation throughout the measurement campaign, which is 0.14%. The standard uncertainty $u(\Delta T)$ in the temperature difference is taken from the average peak-to-peak variation in the ambient temperature from the climate-control system, 0.1 K. Finally, the uncertainties $u(\alpha_\Phi)$ and $u(\alpha_T)$ in the correction coefficients are taken as the standard errors of the corresponding regression slopes according to [12].

From table 5, we find a final corrected IQD of -73 ppm \pm 34 ppm. Within this uncertainty interval

and the known insignificant IQD of the photodiode, the experimental result is consistent with the simulations, which predict an apparent IQD of -72 ppm at $y = 0$ mm for a wire-bond diameter of 30 μ m and an adhesive-layer thickness of 1 μ m.

Overall, the simulations reproduce several key features observed experimentally. In particular, the thermal time constants agree well, with a simulated value of 117 s compared to an experimentally estimated value of 123 s. The simulated offset in apparent IQD arising from the module design is also consistent with the measurements. However, quantitative discrepancies remain. The simulated thermal responsivity (482 KW $^{-1}$) is lower than the experimentally determined value (667 KW $^{-1}$), and the experimentally observed dependence of the apparent IQD on optical power level and ambient temperature is not captured by the current simulation model. For these reasons, the simulations are not used quantitatively to correct the measured IQD, but rather to provide qualitative insight into design-related effects and sensitivities.

There is therefore clear potential for improvement in the module design. Employing thinner wire bonds between the heater and the PCB would significantly reduce the sensitivity to adhesive-layer thickness

and improve robustness with respect to fabrication variability.

The uncertainty analysis shows that the dominant contribution arises from the uncertainty of the average IQD within a single measurement series. This uncertainty is primarily governed by the additional term originating from the spread in IQD values at different beam positions y . To further reduce the uncertainty in the corrected IQD, it is therefore essential to understand the origin of this spread. As discussed earlier, the variation may stem from aspects of the data analysis or from temperature-related effects within the measurement setup. Both possibilities should be investigated in more detail in future work.

5. Conclusion

We have presented a new generation of room-temperature dual-mode modules designed to reduce thermal non-equivalence between optical and electrical heating. The revised design, featuring a backside resistive heater and an improved thermal conduction path, substantially decreases sensitivity to beam position and enables accurate characterisation of the remaining dependencies on optical power level and relative temperature.

By quantifying these effects, we obtain a corrected IQD of -73 ± 34 ppm (measuring at the center of the diode with $748 \mu\text{W}$ optical power), which represents the lowest uncertainty achieved with a dual-mode photodiode operated at room temperature. This result is consistent with finite-element simulations, although the simulations underestimate both the absolute temperature rise and the power dependence observed experimentally. These discrepancies indicate that radiative heat transfer and other subtle thermal effects are not yet fully captured in the current model.

Further improvements in module design—particularly thinner wire bonds to reduce sensitivity to adhesive-layer thickness—and refinement of the thermal model are expected to reduce uncertainties even further. Together, these developments strengthen the case for compact, self-calibrating photodiodes as practical alternatives to cryogenic radiometers in applications requiring traceable optical power measurements.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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